

Table S4. Pharmacologic compounds used for Ussing chamber measurements

	Site of addition (Apical/Basolateral)	Pharmacological activity	Supplier	Catalogue number
Amiloride	A	Inhibit Epithelial sodium channels (ENaC)	Sigma-Aldrich	Cat#A7410
Forskolin	A and B	cAMP activator (activate CFTR)	Sigma-Aldrich	Cat#F6886
IBMX (3-Isobutyl- 1-methylxanthine)	A and B	Phosphodiesterase inhibitor	Sigma-Aldrich	Cat#I5879
CFTRInh-172	A	CFTR inhibitor	Selleckchem	Cat#S7139
ATP	A	Calcium activated chloride channel activator (CaCC)	Sigma-Aldrich	Cat#A2383